

CORRESPONDENCE BETWEEN MAMLUKS
AND TIMURIDS IN THE FIFTEENTH CENTURY:
AN UNPUBLISHED CORPUS OF OFFICIAL LETTERS
(BNF, MS. AR. 4440)¹

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The historiography of Mamluk-Timurid relations has almost always sprung from the accounts left by contemporary authors and scholars through their histories and chronicles. With this article, I would like to introduce a source neglected all too long, namely, the ms. ar. 4440 (BnF, Paris). A collection of letters (*munša'a*), this manuscript belongs to the genre of documentary sources and bears great significance for the study of diplomatic exchanges between the Mamluks and Timurids in the mid-15th century. Indeed, the letters it preserves provide a considerable amount of data never mentioned before in the historical works of the period.

This study consists of two parts. The first is devoted to the presentation of the ms. ar. 4440 and the Mamluk-Timurid material it contains. I will also offer a brief overview of these dynasties' relations prior to 842/1438-9 (Jaqmaq's accession to the sultanate), before moving on to the period covered by the corpus. By comparing these letters with the Mamluk chronicles, I will describe diplomatic exchanges between the Timurids and Sultan Jaqmaq. In the second part of this article, I will focus on the corpus itself as an administrative source, analyzing it from the perspective of diplomatics. Scholars within the field of Arabic and Islamic Studies may have devoted some attention to this discipline as of late, but the ground for such analysis remains fertile and largely unbroken. Although the framework of this precludes a complete study of diplomatics under the Mamluks, I will nevertheless seek to demonstrate how this discipline can elucidate the reality of diplomatic exchanges between two dynasties in the premodern Islamic world. To do so, I will focus on particular aspects of

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those rules for letter composition – as set out by the Mamluk chancery – that aim to establish correspondents’ status. Finally, I will compare said rules to the Mamluk-Timurid corpus of ms. ar. 4440 and conclude with an evaluation of dynastic relations based upon the reading grid furnished by the discipline of diplomatics.

I. AN UNPUBLISHED CORPUS: BNF MS. AR. 4440

In 2007, F. Bauden published an article dedicated to diplomatic conventions in the Islamic world,² revealing his “rediscovery” of a manuscript at the Bibliothèque nationale de France (ms. ar. 4440). Though noted in the past, this manuscript – compiled by an anonymous secretary who must have worked at the Cairo chancery in the second half of the 15th century – ostensibly fell into oblivion.³ Along with the *Qahwat al-inšā’* of Ibn Hiğğah,⁴ these letters constitute a major source for the study of diplomatic relations between Muslim powers in this period. Indeed, if we exclude the third part of the work,⁵ ms. ar. 4440 offers a remarkable range of unpublished correspondence⁶ exchanged between the Mamluk sultans on the one hand⁷ and the Ottomans, Timurids, Qara Qoyunlu, Hafids of Tunis, Qaramanids of Konya, Ayyubid Emirate of Ḥiṣn Kayfā, Kingdom of Granada, Rasulid Sultanate of Yemen, Golden Horde, Sultan of Malwa, ruler of Crimea, Aq Qoyunlu, and Sultan of Takrūr, Cyprus and Lisbon on the other.⁸

The Mamluk-Timurid material in the manuscript consists of ten letters total (six sent from and four received by Cairo – see table 1 below). For

² Bauden, F., “Les Relations diplomatiques entre les sultans mamlouks circassiens et les autres pouvoirs du Dār al-Islām. L’apport du ms. ar. 4440 (BNF, Paris)”, *Annales Islamologiques*, XLI (2007): pp. 1-29.

³ See Colin, G.S., “Contribution à l’étude des relations diplomatiques entre les musulmans d’Occident et l’Égypte au XV^e siècle”, in *Mélanges Maspero*: III. *Orient islamique* (Le Caire: Institut Français d’archéologie orientale, 1953): pp. 197-206; Darrāj, A., “Risālatān bayna sultān Mālwah wa al-Ašraf Qāyṭbāy”, *Revue de l’Institut des manuscrits arabes*, IV (1958/1377): pp. 97-123; Ḥ. Zayyāt, “Aṭar unuf: nuṣṣa qiṣṣa waradat ilā al-abwāb al-šarīfa al-sultāniyya al-malakiyya Īnāl min al-muslimīn al-qāṭinīn Lišbūna”, *Machriq*, XXXV (1937): pp. 13-22.

⁴ The BnF ms. ar. 4440 also includes parts of this book in its third part (fols. 86b-156b); see Bauden, “Les Relations diplomatiques”: pp. 5-6.

⁵ See previous note.

⁶ 62 letters in all.

⁷ The manuscript covers the sultanates of Jaqmaq (842-57/1438-53), Īnāl (857-65/1453-61), Ḥuṣqadam (865-72/1461-7) and the beginning of Qāyṭbāy’s reign (872-901/1468-96). The most recent letters date from 873/1468.

⁸ For details of these letters, see Bauden, “Les Relations diplomatiques”: pp. 7-8.

consistency purposes, I will set aside the three later sent by Sulṭān-Abū Sa‘īd (r. 855-73/1451-69)⁹ and concentrate on the correspondence between Sultan Jaqmaq (r. 842-57/1438-53) and the Šāhruḥids: Šāh Ruḥ (r. 811-50/1409-47), his son Muḥammad Jūkī (d. 848/1444-5) and his grandson ‘Alā’ al-Dawla (d. 865/1460),¹⁰ that is, letters V, XXIV, XLI, XLII, XLIII, XLIV, and LXII.

Letter number ¹¹	Foliation	Sender > Addressee	Date ¹²	Nature
V	ff. 44a-45b	Jaqmaq > Šāh Ruḥ	842/1439	initial letter
XXIV	ff. 65a-66b	Jaqmaq > Muḥammad Jūkī	[844/1440?]	response
XXXIX	ff. 167a-169b	Sulṭān-Abū Sa‘īd > Ḥuṣqadam	867/1462	initial letter
XLI	ff. 171b-172b	Šāh Ruḥ > Jaqmaq	846/1442	initial letter
XLII	ff. 172b-175a	Jaqmaq > Šāh Ruḥ	[847/1443?]	response
XLIII	ff. 175a-177a	Jaqmaq > ‘Alā’ al-Dawla	[846/1442-3?]	response
XLIV	ff. 177a-178b	Jaqmaq > ‘Alā’ al-Dawla	[848/1444]	response
XLVII	ff. 184b-187a	Sulṭān-Abū Sa‘īd > Ḥuṣqadam	[865-72/1461-7?]	initial letter
XLVIII	ff. 187a-191a	Sulṭān-Abū Sa‘īd > Ḥuṣqadam	868/1464: written 870/1465: received	initial letter
LXII	ff. 210a-210b	Jaqmaq > Muḥammad Jūkī	[846/1442?]	response

Table 1. List of letters (ms. ar. 4440)

The period covered by the corpus (842-848/1438-1445) proves particularly significant for the study of Mamluk-Timurid relations. Indeed, after a long history of tensions and struggles, the accession of Jaqmaq to the sultanate (842/1438) inaugurated a new phase of peace between the two powers, characterized by mutual recognition and respect: it was during this period that the practice of diplomacy assumed its full meaning. The corpus provides a unique witness to such change, which along with evidence from the historical works, illuminates these developments profoundly. Before investigation of that period’s details,

⁹ The three letters sent by Sulṭān-Abū Sa‘īd deal with a later stage of Mamluk-Timurid relationships that lie beyond the scope of this article.

¹⁰ During the reign of Šāh Ruḥ, these last two held the positions of governor of Ḥuttalān and *amīr-i dīvān*, respectively.

¹¹ These numbers follow the system by Bauden, “Les Relations diplomatiques”: pp. 15-23.

¹² The dates written between [] are the dates that I attributed to the letters in my own study (See Ph.D. Thesis). However, some of them (indicated with a question mark) still require comparison with analysis of Persian sources.

however, one should remember the difficult past related to the exchanges between the Mamluks and the Timurids.

Historical overview

The inauguration of exchange between the Mamluk sultan Barqūq and Tīmūr Barlas or Tamerlane at the end of the 8th/14th century is an important turning point in Mamluk history. For the first time since the collapse of the Ilkhanid dynasty (after 736/1335), the Mamluks had to face a significant threat to their sovereignty, one which brought back to life the old struggle for supremacy – a struggle that had characterized their previous relationship with the Mongols. Since their first contacts, diplomatic exchanges betray the tensions between the two rulers. These tensions culminates into outright hostility when Barqūq ordered the murder of the Timurid emissaries (795/1393).¹³ This action violated the traditional immunity of emissaries and qualified as an unforgivable offense within the Mongolian tradition:¹⁴ accordingly, Tīmūr's reaction was not long in coming. Only two years after Barqūq's death, Tīmūr led his troops to Syria and defeated the Mamluk army in Aleppo and Damascus (803/1400).

Beside the military rout, the young sultan Faraj (r. 801-8/1399-1405; 808-15/1405-12) also had to face other kind of humiliation when, for example, Tīmūr sent his first official embassy to Cairo in early Jumādā II 805/late December 1402. This embassy was led by his emissary Kh^wāja Nizām al-Dīn Mas'ūd Kujujānī¹⁵ who carried a letter and a golden flag with the name of his master written upon it.¹⁶ The following year, in Muḥarram 806/July-August 1403, the same emissary paraded through the Mamluk capital on an elephant bearing two green flags, the color of Tīmūr.¹⁷ Among the gifts he brought to Faraj were a robe¹⁸ and a crown,¹⁹ both symbols of

¹³ Broadbridge, A.F., *Kingship and Ideology in the Islamic and Mongol Worlds*, (Cambridge: University Press, 2008): pp. 177-80.

¹⁴ Sinor, D., "Diplomatic Practices in Medieval Inner Asia", in Bosworth, C.E. (ed.), *The Islamic World from Classical to Modern Times. Essays in Honor of Bernard Lewis* (Princeton: Darwin Press, 1989): pp. 343-6.

¹⁵ The reading of this name is sometimes different. Al-Maqrīzī, *Al-Sulūk li ma'rifat duwal al-mulūk* (ed. S. 'A.-F. 'Āšūr, Cairo: Dār al-Kutub, 2007): III/3, p. 1098: كججاني, or كججاني: ibid., p. 1111; Al-Saḥāwī, *Al-Ḍaw' al-lāmi' li ahl al-qarn al-tāsi'* (Cairo: Maktabat al-Qudsī, 1934-6): X, p. 157.

¹⁶ Al-'Asqalānī, *Inbā' al-ḡumr bi abnā' al-'umr* (ed. Ḥ. Ḥabašī, Cairo: Lajnat ihyā' al-turāṭ al-islāmī, 1969-72): II, p. 229. Also in al-Maqrīzī, *Al-Sulūk*: III/3, pp. 1098-9, but with no mention of the flag.

¹⁷ The colors of Tīmūr. Al-Maqrīzī, *Al-Sulūk*: III/3, p. 1111; al-'Asqalānī, *Inbā' al-ḡumr*: II, p. 256.

¹⁸ Ibn Qāḍī Šuhbah, *Tārīḥ* (ed. 'A. Darwīš, Damascus: Institut français de Damas,

Tīmūr's claim over the Mamluks. This embassy left Cairo some time later,²⁰ carrying the promise that the forts constituting the northern border of the Mamluk territory would be abandoned.²¹

Shortly afterwards, Tīmūr's death (807/1405) plunged his empire into a series of internal struggles that left the field open for the gradual emancipation of the conquered states, including Mamluk Egypt and Syria. Although Šāh Ruḥ managed to seize power in 811/1409, the problems internal to his realm occupied him on other fronts from 817/1414 to 823/1420-1.²² Thus, in 820/1417, sultan al-Mu'ayyad Šayḥ (r. 815-24/1412-21) launched a military campaign to recover the lost territories to the north, which had fallen into the hands of Turkmen dynasties (the Qaramanids and Dulqadirids) since the time of Tīmūr's conquests. During a second expedition in 822/1419, Mamluk troops, led by the sultan's son, seized the Qaramanid city Kayseri, where the sultan's name was proclaimed in the *ḥuṭba* (Friday prayer) and where Mamluk sovereignty was finally reaffirmed.

Although Šāh Ruḥ must have known about the Mamluk revival and events in Anatolia, he apparently sent no embassy to Cairo until 24 Rabī' I 823/8 April 1420.²³ Envoys are mentioned again the next year, Rajab 824/July 1421, along with news of Šāh Ruḥ's victory over the Qara Qoyunlu

1997): IV, p. 312, notes that the embassy arrived in Damascus in Dū al-Qa' da 805/ June-July 1403, bringing gifts to the sultan such as a robe referred to as *qabā'* (Kazimirski, *Dictionnaire arabe-français* [Beyrouth: Albouraq, 2004]: II, p. 670: «Robe d'homme à manches, plus juste à la taille que la houppelande»). Al-'Asqalānī, *Inbā' al-ġumr*: II, p. 256, says: «malbūs li 'l-sultāni 'alā šūrati 'l-ḥil'a lahu mina 'l-Lank bi an yakūna nā'ibahu 'alā 'l-diyār al-miṣriyyah wa 'l-šāmiyyah».

¹⁹ Ibn Qāḍī Šuhbah, *Tārīḥ*: IV, p. 312.

²⁰ Al-Maqrīzī, *Al-Sulūk*: III/3, pp. 1117, 1120: reception for the departure on 27 Rabī' I 806/14 October 1403; Ibn Qāḍī Šuhbah, *Tārīḥ*: IV, p. 352: 2 Ša'bān 806/14 February 1404. The embassy stopped first in Damascus on his way back home on 7 Ramaḍān 806/19 March 1404. Ibid.: IV, pp. 356-7; Al-'Asqalānī, *Inbā' al-ġumr*: II, p. 262: Rajab 806/ January-February 1404.

²¹ Al-Qalqašandī, *Šubḥ al-a'sā fī šinā'at al-inšā'* (ed. M. 'A. al-Q. Ḥātim, Cairo: al-Mu'assasa al-miṣriyya al-'amma li'ta'lif wa 'l-tarjama wa 'l-ṭibā'a wa 'l-našr, 1963): VII, pp. 325-31. He abandoned the forts of Elbistan, Malatya, Gerger, Kahta, Qal'at al-Rūm et al-Bīrah, and he even offered to abandon the cities of Aleppo and Damascus. Broadbridge, *Kingship and Ideology*: p. 196: according to Persian sources, the embassy left Cairo with the tribute due to Tīmūr. Mamluk sources mention nothing but gifts (like a giraffe).

²² In Fārs against his nephews Iskandar and Rustam and in Azerbaijan and Iraq against the Qara Qoyunlu, Qarā Yūsuf and then his son Iskandar.

²³ Al-Maqrīzī, *Al-Sulūk*: IV/1, p. 425. Unfortunately we have no information about the purpose of this embassy.

and his capture of Tabrīz,²⁴ but he apparently made no claim to sovereignty over the Mamluks. On the contrary, according to the letters in Ibn Hījja's collections, both powers seem to have maintained good relations with each other. Little extant information illuminates Šāh Ruḥ's first claim of sovereignty over his neighbors. Two years after rising as the sole ruler of Tīmūr's kingdom (814/1411),²⁵ he received embassies²⁶ not only from the Uzbeks, the rulers of Qipchaq, Šīrvān (Golestan), Hazārjarīb (Isfahan), Sarī (Mazandaran), Fīrūzkūh (Teheran), Garmsīr et Qandahār (Afghanistan)²⁷ but also from the Aq Qoyunlu, the Sultans of Delhi, the lords of Hurmuz, and, at least at the beginning of his reign, from the Ottomans.²⁸

Barsbāy's accession to the throne (r. 825-41/1422-38) was a milestone in the Mamluks' relations with the Timurids, especially regarding their struggle for predominance in the Hījāz.²⁹ The eleven years of "epistolary war" concerning the sending of the Timurid *Kiswa* reflects this dynamic quite well.³⁰ In the year 833/1429-30,³¹ Barsbāy was addressed as *amīr*, not sultan, by Šāh Ruḥ, who, in 838/1435,³² also threatened to enter Mamluk territory on his way to visit Jerusalem, and further protested against

²⁴ Al-'Asqalānī, *Inbā' al-ġumr*: III, pp. 249-50. Ibn Hījjah, *Qahwat al-inšā'* (ed. Veselý, R., Berlin: Klaus Schwarz Verlag, 2005): pp. 315-20 and Id., *Šams al-maġrib fī 'l-murqīš al-muṭrib* (ms. Sprenger 1223; Berlin, Staatsbibliothek, Orientabteilung, ff 31b-32a; presents a letter on the same subject, which arrived in Cairo in late Muḥarram 824/January 1421 and was written to al-Mu'ayyad Šayḥ. In any case, Šāh Ruḥ addressed the Mamluk sultan as his equal and he used the formula *al-maqām al-šarīf*.

²⁵ Date of the death of Ḥalīl-Sultān, Šāh Ruḥ's major opponent.

²⁶ All sent for the purpose of recognizing and submitting to the sovereign.

²⁷ Jackson, P. & Lockhart, L. (eds.), *The Cambridge History of Iran: VI. The Timurid and Safavid Periods* (Cambridge: University Press, 1986): p. 102.

²⁸ Forbes Manz, B., "Šāh Rukh", *EF*: IX, p. 197: she does not mention any dates for these embassies.

²⁹ Barsbāy's politics in the Hījāz is characterized by the establishment of a monopoly over the transit trade as well as an intensification of the seasonal control over the region. Meloy, J.L., *Imperial Power and Maritime Trade. Mecca and Cairo in the Later Middle Ages* (Chicago: MEDOC, 2010).

³⁰ I am currently preparing an article on this issue and the reevaluation of Mamluk-Timurid relationships.

³¹ Al-'Aynī, *'Iqd al-jumān fī tāriḥ ahl al-zamān* (ed. 'A. al-R. al-Ṭanṭāwī, Cairo: al-Zahrā' li 'l-i'lām al-'arabī, 1989): p. 376; Al-Šayrafī, *Nuzhat al-nufūs wa 'l-abdān fī tawāriḥ al-zamān* (ed. Ḥ. Ḥabašī, Cairo: al-Hay'a al-miṣriyya al-'amma li'l-kitāb, 1970-94); IV, p. 197; al-'Asqalānī, *Inbā' al-ġumr*: III, p. 440. Al-Maqrīzī, *Al-Sulūk*: IV/2, p. 833: description of the letter.

³² Al-Maqrīzī, *Al-Sulūk*: IV/2, p. 946 and *ibid.*: IV/3, p. 1187 and Ibn Taġrībīrdī, *Al-Nujūm al-zāhira fī mulūk Miṣr wa 'l-Qāhira* (Cairo: Dār al-kutub, 2005-6²): XV, p. 59. This source adds that Šāh Ruḥ also complained of the bribes paid to judges.

Barsbāy's customs policy in Jidda. The year 839/1435-6 is marked by the symbolic reaffirmation of Timurid sovereignty over the lands previously conquered by Tīmūr: in Šafar/September,³³ Šāh Ruḥ sent robes of investiture to the Ottomans, Qaramanids, Dulqadirids, Aq Qoyunlu, and no later than Jumādā II 839/January 1436,³⁴ it was Barsbāy's turn to receive – as his predecessor Faraj had before him – a robe and crown along with the request to mention Šāh Ruḥ's name in the *ḥuṭba* and mint coins in his name as well.

Despite Barsbāy's mistreatment of the Timurid emissaries, Šāh Ruḥ did not react with force, nor does he seem to have renewed his claims over the Mamluks unlike the Ottomans, who received three more robes in 842/1438-9.³⁵ In fact, Barsbāy's death (841/1438) and Jaqmaq's succession to the throne (842/1438) were both watersheds in the powers' relationships, constituting a real change such that old grievances and struggles seem to have given way to a cordial *entente* between the two rulers. While neither party abandoned their own claims,³⁶ both nevertheless offered a mutual recognition and respect that would last until Šāh Ruḥ's death in 850/1447. Evidence of this transition clearly emerges from the Mamluk chronicles, which transmit many accounts of Timurid embassy reception in Cairo, as well as the letters preserved in ms. ar. 4440.

Jaqmaq's time

Reviewing all Mamluk sources covering this period, I have found that, the reign of Jaqmaq, when compared to others, is marked by a high frequency of embassy exchange. Indeed, between his accession in 842/1438 and Šāh Ruḥ's death in 850/1447, diplomatic contacts between the two realms proceeded annually.³⁷ Comparison of the letters in ms. ar. 4440 with the Mamluk chronicles provides the material for a vivid portrait of these exchanges. Table 2 records the various Timurid embassies that reached Cairo during the period in question as well as the letters of ms. ar. 4440.

³³ Al-Maqrīzī, *Al-Sulūk*: IV/2, p. 957 and Ibn Taġrībirdī, *Al-Nujūm al-zāhira*: XV, p. 63.

³⁴ Al-Maqrīzī, *Al-Sulūk*: IV/2, p. 969 and Ibn Taġrībirdī, *Al-Nujūm al-zāhira*: XV, p. 73. Angrier still, the sultan maltreated the ambassador. Šāh Ruḥ's claims provoked an exchange of embassies between the Mamluks and the Ottomans to establish an alliance against the Timurids (see al-Maqrīzī, *al-Sulūk*: IV/2, p. 969). However, we have no more details concerning this alliance.

³⁵ Al-Maqrīzī, *Al-Sulūk*: IV/3, p. 1103. In this case, as in the preceding, it is not clear whether Murād II wore the robes or not.

³⁶ Particularly over the Ḥijāz.

³⁷ The last embassy mentioned in the chronicles was sent in 848/1444. At that time, Šāh Ruḥ became seriously ill but also preoccupied with internal revolts.

Date	Purpose
Ramaḍān 842/ February 1439	Letter V (fols. 44a-45b): Announcement of Jaqmaq's accession to the throne and expression of desire to maintain good relationships between the two states. (Arrival to Herat in 843/1439).
Jumādā I 843/ October 1439 ³⁸ or beginning of Jumādā II 843/ November 1439 ³⁹	Timurid embassy to Cairo to congratulate the new sultan Jaqmaq.
27 Rabī' I 844/ 26 August 1440 ⁴⁰ or 26 Rabī' II 844/ 24 September 1440 ⁴¹	Return of the first Mamluk embassy (842/1439) accompanied by Timurid emissaries; congratulations to the sultan Jaqmaq and expression of the good wishes and intentions of Šāh Ruḥ.
28 Rabī' II 844/ 26 September 1440 ⁴²	Presence of an embassy from Muḥammad Jūkī at the same time as Šāh Ruḥ's.
[844/1440?]	Letter XXIV (fols. 65a-66b): Jaqmaq's response to Muḥammad Jūkī's letter concerning his nomination as heir apparent and the troubles caused by the Aq Qoyunlu emir Ḥamza.
Ša'bān-Ramaḍān 845/ December 1441- February 1442 ⁴³	Arrival in Cairo of a Timurid šayḥ, Šams al-Dīn Muḥammad al-Ḥāfi al-Ḥanafi, ⁴⁴ who wanted to make the pilgrimage.

³⁸ According to Ibn Taḡrībirdī, *Al-Nujūm al-zāhira*: XV, p. 33; Ibn Iyās, *Badā'i' al-zuhūr fī waqā'i' al-duhūr* (ed. M. Muṣṭafā, Cairo: Dār al-Kutub, 2008²): II, p. 221.

³⁹ Al-Maqrīzī, *Al-Sulūk*: IV/3, pp. 1175-6; al-'Aynī, *Iqd al-jumān*: p. 549; Al-'Asqalānī, *Inbā' al-ḡumr*: IV, p. 132; Al-Šayrafī, *Nuzhat al-nufūs*: IV, p. 164; 'Abd al-Bāsiṭ b. Ḥalīl, *Nayl al-amal fī ḡayl al-duwal* (ed. 'U. 'A. al-Salām Tadmūrī (Sidon- Beirut: al-Maktaba al-'Aṣriyya, 2002): V, p. 106.

⁴⁰ Al-'Aynī, *Iqd al-jumān*: p. 559-60: I believe this author confused the two months.

⁴¹ Al-'Asqalānī, *Inbā' al-ḡumr*: IV, p. 157: this author states that news of the embassy's arrival was known earlier. Al-Maqrīzī, *Al-Sulūk*: IV/3, p. 1208; Al-Šayrafī, *Nuzhat al-nufūs*: IV, pp. 198-9; Ibn Taḡrībirdī, *Al-Nujūm al-zāhira*: XV, pp. 342-3; 'Abd al-Bāsiṭ b. Ḥalīl, *Nayl al-amal*: V, p. 122: this author does not state the day.

⁴² Al-Maqrīzī, *Al-Sulūk*: IV/3, p. 1209; al-Šayrafī, *Nuzhat al-nufūs*: IV, pp. 199-200.

⁴³ Al-'Aynī, *Iqd al-jumān*: p. 572; Al-Šayrafī, *Nuzhat al-nufūs*: IV, pp. 239-40; Ibn Taḡrībirdī, *Al-Nujūm al-zāhira*: XV, p. 350; Id., *Ḥawādiṯ al-duhūr fī madā 'l-ayyām wa 'l-šuhūr* (ed. F.M. Šaltūt, Cairo: Lajnat ihyā' al-turāṯ al-islāmī, 1990): p. 35; al-Saḥāwī, *Al-Tibr al-masbūk fī ḡayl al-Sulūk* (ed. S. 'A.-F. 'Āšūr, Cairo: Dār al-Kutub, 2002-7): I, pp. 62-3.

⁴⁴ He belonged to Ulūḡ Beg's court in Samarqand. He was also a well-estimated jurist for Šāh Ruḥ. Al-Šayrafī, *Nuzhat al-nufūs*: IV, pp. 239-40; Ibn Taḡrībirdī, *Al-Nujūm al-zāhira*: XV, p. 350; Id., *Ḥawādiṯ al-duhūr*: p. 35; al-Saḥāwī, *Al-Tibr al-masbūk*: I, pp. 62-3.

[846/1442-3?]	Jaqmaq's response to 'Alā' al-Dawla concerning his joy for the šayḥ's return from his pilgrimage.
Ša'bān 846/December 1442 ⁴⁵	A Timurid embassy arrived in Cairo
	Letter XLI (fols. 171b-172b) arrived on 14 Ša'bān 846/18 December 1442; written on 2 Rabī' I 846/11 July 1442): Reminder to Jaqmaq of Šāh Ruḥ's past desire to send the inner <i>kiswa</i> for the Ka'ba.
[846/1442-3?]	Letter LXII (fols. 210a-210b): Jaqmaq's answer to Muḥammad Jūkī's letter. Confirmation that the Mamluk sultan accepted Šāh Ruḥ's request concerning the inner <i>kiswa</i> and that Šāh Ruḥ's emissary had already returned with this message.
27 Jumādā II 847/ 22 October 1443 ⁴⁶	A Timurid embassy arrived in Cairo to discuss the <i>kiswa</i> matter with the Sultan. ⁴⁷
[847/1443?]	Letter XLII (fols. 172b-175a): Jaqmaq's response to Šāh Ruḥ's two letters concerning the sending of the inner <i>kiswa</i> and the money issued from the <i>awqāf</i> of his realm; approval of the Mamluk sultan of both requests.
Ša'bān 848/November 1444 ⁴⁸	Arrival of a huge Timurid delegation bringing the inner <i>kiswa</i> to Cairo.
	Letter XLIV (fols. 177a-178b): Jaqmaq's answer to 'Alā' al-Dawla given to those Timurid šayḥs bringing the inner <i>kiswa</i> before they left for Mecca. Proof of the Mamluk sultan's fulfillment of Šāh Ruḥ's wish; description of the šayḥs' process to the Holy Cities.

Table 2. Timurid embassies in Cairo

⁴⁵ Ibn Taḡrībīrdī, *Ḥawādīṭ al-duḥūr*: p. 49 (*quṣṣād min 'indi Šāh Ruḥ*); 'Abd al-Bāsiṭ b. Ḥalīl, *Nayl al-amal*: V, pp. 164-5 (*qāšid awlād Šāh Ruḥ*); al-Saḥāwī, *Al-Tibr al-masbūk*: I, p. 118 (*quṣṣād min 'indi awlād Šāh Ruḥ*); Ibn Iyās, *Badā'ī' al-zuhūr*: II, p. 236 (*qāšid awlād Šāh Ruḥ*). On 6 Ša'bān/10 December: Al-'Aynī, *'Iqd al-jumān*: p. 584 (*quṣṣād min 'indi awlād Šāh Ruḥ*); al-Šayrafī, *Nuzhat al-nufūs*: IV, p. 256 (*quṣṣād Ibn Šāh Ruḥ*).

⁴⁶ Al-'Aynī, *'Iqd al-jumān*: p. 600; al-Šayrafī, *Nuzhat al-nufūs*: IV, p. 277; Ibn Taḡrībīrdī, *Ḥawādīṭ al-duḥūr*: p. 64; al-Saḥāwī, *Al-Tibr al-masbūk*: I, p. 164.

⁴⁷ We learn about the purpose of the present mission in the description of the reception of another embassy which arrived in the following year (848/1444): Ibn Taḡrībīrdī, *Ḥawādīṭ al-duḥūr*: p. 76; Id., *Al-Nujūm al-zāhira*: XV, p. 364; al-'Aynī, *'Iqd al-jumān*: p. 627.

⁴⁸ In Ša'bān/November (day not specified): Ibn Iyās, *Badā'ī' al-zuhūr*: II, pp. 244-5. On 14 Ša'bān/26 November: al-'Aynī, *'Iqd al-jumān*: p. 627. On 15 Ša'bān/27 November: Ibn Taḡrībīrdī, *Ḥawādīṭ al-duḥūr*: p. 76 et Id., *Al-Nujūm al-zāhira*: XV, p. 364. Al-Saḥāwī, *Wajīz al-kalām fī 'l-ḡayl 'alā duwal al-islām* (ed. B. 'A. Ma'rūf, Ġ.F. al-Ḥarastānī, A. al-Ḥaṭīmī, Beirut: Mu'assasat al-Risāla, 1995): II, pp. 594-5 et Id., *Al-Tibr al-masbūk*: I, pp. 215-7: 14 Ramaḍān/25 December; 'Abd al-Bāsiṭ b. Ḥalīl, *Nayl al-amal*: V, pp. 194-5: Ramaḍān/December.

Analysis of the corpus in conjunction with the Mamluk chronicles proves significant in several regards. First of all, it helps to place each letter in its diplomatic context and, thanks to description given by Mamluk authors, can further aid in securing dates for letters otherwise undated. Moreover, the letters state information mentioned in the chronicles more precisely, not only confirming and opposing them (dates of arrival, emissaries' name, the missions' purpose), but also offering data unknown to the chroniclers at times (e.g., the presence of gifts and their details). Finally, from a historical point of view, the corpus provides previously unknown information concerning the Mamluk sultan's place as patron and protector of Islam and Muslims (the inner *kiswa* matter and the protection of Timurid pilgrims), Mamluk foreign policy towards their neighbors (to keep the roads safe and secure for traders and travelers), and Timurid internal history (Šāh Ruḥ's succession and Timurid's patronage).⁴⁹

From a diplomatic perspective, both the corpus and Mamluk sources present a detailed picture of emissary reception in Cairo along with its concomitant *etiquette*,⁵⁰ which thereby assists the determination Mamluk-Timurid relations after Jaqmaq's ascent. The choice of emissaries, their arrival in Cairo and reception at the Citadel, the exchanges of gifts, and the moneys and food granted to the emissaries during their stay in the Mamluk capital all demonstrate the high position that the Timurid ruler acquired in the eyes of the Mamluks at this time. However, even if these criteria shed light on the state of their relationships, establishing the precise status of the Timurids still requires a theoretical framework. Diplomats provided such a grid through the study of Mamluk chancery practice. Indeed, a survey of chancery manuals available from the period reveals that most of the rules associated with letter composition depend on the status of the addressee—a status established by the Mamluk chancery. The chancery manual constitutes a genre between the anthology (to which ms. ar. 4440 belongs) and the *artes* or *summae dictaminis*, for it juxtaposes samples of letters or other chancery documents with theoretical explanations that disclose the rules of the chancery. These handbooks for scribes are true mines of information for document study since they provide the key necessary for a proper understanding of diplomatic rules. Analysis of these manuals allows us to lay the foundation of a Status Guide that could help expand and refine our understanding of the state of relations between Mamluks and other Muslims dynasties beyond the textual meanings conveyed in documents.

⁴⁹ These three points were studied in my Ph.D. dissertation *Le Caire, carrefour des ambassades* (Part 1, Chapter 2).

⁵⁰ See *Le Caire, carrefour des ambassades* (Part 1, Chapter 1).

II. DIPLOMATIC ANALYSIS

a. Sources

Five main chancery manuals pertain to the whole Mamluk period: two for the Turkish period, *al-Ta'rif bi'l-muṣṭalaḥ al-šarīf* of Ibn Faḍl Allāh al-'Umarī (700-49/1301-49)⁵¹ and *Tatqīf al-ta'rif bi'l-muṣṭalaḥ al-šarīf* of Ibn Nāzīr al-Jayš (726-86/1326-84);⁵² and three for the Circassian period, *Ṣubḥ al-a'šā fī šinā'at al-inšā'* of al-Qalqašandī (756-821/1355-1418), *al-Taḡr al-bāsim fī šinā'at al-kātib wa 'l-kātim* of al-Saḥmāwī (d. 868/1463),⁵³ and *Qalā'id al-jumān fī muṣṭalaḥ mukātabāt ahl al-zamān* of Ibn al-Qalqašandī (797-876/1395-1471).⁵⁴ Since the first three have figured prominently in academic discussion, I will devote my attention to the last two mentioned, both from the Circassian period.

For a long time *al-Taḡr al-bāsim* was attributed to a different author, al-Ḥālidī, under the title *al-Maqṣid al-rafi' al-munša' al-hādī li dīwān al-inšā'*, also known as *Dīwān al-inšā'* in the scientific literature. Recently, however, the author's identity and book's title have come to light.⁵⁵ Al-Saḥmāwī was a secretary at the chancery of Cairo from Barsbāy's sultanate (r. 825-41/1422-37) until Ināl's (r. 857-65/1453-60) when he wrote the manual, which continues the work of al-Qalqašandī. This book is fundamental for any inquiry into diplomatics since it covers the period concerned by ms. ar. 4440 and the author provides a number of contemporary rules and unpublished letter samples.

The other work, *Qalā'id al-jumān*, is the product of al-Qalqašandī's son, who also worked as a secretary but in the service of Mamluk emirs. His book deals primarily with semi-official letters (*iḥwāniyyāt*) but handles official correspondence as well. However, concerning this second category, Ibn al-Qalqašandī presents almost no new data compared to his predecessors, which thus diminishes the work's importance for the present study. Although my central interest concerns the Circassian period, the Turkish chancery manuals still need to be examined, for al-'Umarī and Ibn Nāzīr al-Jayš established the fundamental rules that determine the writing of official correspondence. Moreover the authors of the Circassian period demonstrate a substantial reliance on their works.

⁵¹ Ed. S. al-Durūbī, 2 vols, (Al-Karak: Mu'tah University, 1992).

⁵² Ed. R. Vesely, (Cairo: Institut français d'archéologie orientale, 1987).

⁵³ Ed. A.M. Anas Mursī, 2 vols, (Cairo: Dār al-kutub, 2009).

⁵⁴ British Library, ms. OR. 3625. On this author and his manual, see F. Bauden's article in this volume.

⁵⁵ Mursī, A.M.A., made this discovery by comparing ms. ar. 4439 (BnF, Paris) with a different copy of another version of the text kept in Cairo (Dār al-Kutub, ms. 13158 zāy).

b. Theory

First we must consider the identity of the sender and of the person to whom the letter is sent; we must consider whether he is noble or common in rank, a friend or an enemy, then what kind of person he is and of what background. The next consideration is the thing dealt with: is it a just or unjust matter, and is it serious or minor? Next the writer should ask himself what attitude he wishes to project: proud or humble, harsh or forgiving, threatening, stern, or that of a trusted friend.⁵⁶

In his study of letter writing in the Middle Ages, L. Pelerman quotes these words taken from Alberic of Monte Cassino (d. 1088; *Flores Rhetoricæ*). This passage serves a perfect introduction to the main principles that govern the writing of official correspondence within the Mamluk chancery. Indeed, even if this quotation belongs to the Christian West, all Mamluk chancery authors recognize the three standards nonetheless:

1. Knowledge of the addressee's status is, by far, the most important principle, for it determines all the other writing rules. For this reason, the two main manuals for the period under investigation – *Ṣubḥ al-a'šā* and *al-Tağr al-bāsim* – introduce the section on correspondence with a section devoted to the titles (*alqāb* and *nu'ūt*) employed based on the addressee's rank. The use of a specific title sets both internal (opening protocol, invocations, writing style) and external (paper size, opening blank spaces (*ṭurra*, *'alāma*) forms. These patterns were already fixed during the Turkish period, as evident in al-'Umarī and Ibn Nāzīr al-Jayš's manuals, but evolved during the Circassian period in response to political changes in the East.

2. The second principle concerns the letter's subject, which relates to the theme of the letter. In fact, for initial letters, chancery secretaries distinguished 20 different situations in which the sultan could decide to write a letter to someone.⁵⁷ These themes determine the length or brevity of the letters as well as the choice of introduction.

3. The third principle is directly linked to the second: the way in which the author wants to impress the addressee, dimension of composition that belongs to rhetoric and the rules of speech.

In addition to these three standards, a fourth is clearly expressed by al-

⁵⁶ Pelerman, L., "The Medieval Art of Letter Writing. Rhetoric as Institutional Expression", in Bazerman, Ch., & Paradis, J. (eds.), *Textual Dynamics of the Professions. Historical and Contemporary Studies of Writing in Professional Communities* (Madison, Wis.: University of Wisconsin Press, 1991): p. 104.

⁵⁷ Al-Qalqašandī, *Ṣubḥ al-a'šā*: VIII, pp. 233-358. Al-Qalqašandī presents 24 themes, but four were not used anymore when he was working in the chancery.

Qalqašandī in his introduction to the section devoted to letters addressed to Muslims rulers: secretaries should always write following the model of their own letters.⁵⁸ This last rule could explain differences encountered in the production of the Mamluk letters.

In this article, I will examine only the first of these principles, namely, the addressee's status. Under the rubric of diplomatics – i.e., the science dedicated to the tradition, form, and elaboration of written deeds and administrative acts⁵⁹ – I will analyze the main parts of the letters that define an addressee's status. Since this discipline generally works with original documents, its application in the field of Islamic studies can prove particularly challenging. Indeed, only a few original documents from official archives have survived prior to the Ottoman period.⁶⁰ The Mamluk period, however, lies in stark contrast to this paucity of diplomatic material. On the one hand, it has left behind some interesting samples of official documents preserved in recipients' archives, most of them non-Muslim institutions, such as the documents of St. Catherine.⁶¹ On the other hand, it offers a wide range of copies of documents preserved in chancery manuals and anthologies. The combined study of these two groups of sources is essential for investigation into the diplomatics during this period, because even if such study cannot determine the authenticity of documents (one of the goals of diplomatics), it can nonetheless play a crucial role in reconstructing the practices of the Mamluk chancery and the assumed form of original documents as well as – though to a lesser extent – the tradition of chancery acts.

As a complete study of Mamluk diplomatics rests beyond the scope of this particular article, I will only focus on the features of those documents which determine their correspondents' status. These features are both external factors, such as paper size and blank spaces, and internal characteristics like titleholders (*alqāb-nu'ūt*), opening protocol (*iftitāh*), invocation (*du'ā'*), *salutatio*, and finally signature. After description of the rules used in the Mamluk chancery, I will then examine their application in the Mamluk-Timutid letters of ms. ar. 4440.

⁵⁸ Al-Qalqašandī, *Ṣubḥ al-a'šā*: VII, p. 235.

⁵⁹ Cárcel Ortí, M., *Vocabulaire International de la Diplomatie* (Commission Internationale de Diplomatie-Comité International des Sciences Historiques), (València: Universitat de València, 1997): p. 21.

⁶⁰ Bauden, F., "Du destin des archives en Islam. Analyse des données et éléments de réponse", in Aigle, D. and Péquignot, S. (ed.), *La correspondance entre souverains, princes et cités-états. Approches croisées entre l'Orient musulman, l'Occident latin et Byzance (XIII^e-début XVI^e s.)* (Turnhout: Brepols, 2013): pp. 27-49.

⁶¹ For a full list of all records in this period see Bauden, F., "Mamlūk Era Documentary Studies: The State of the Art", *Mamlūk Studies Review*, IX/2 (2005): pp. 15-60.

1. *The paper size* (qaṭ' al-waraq)

Although I mentioned the importance given to titles in the establishment of an addressee's status, there is yet another means, a material one, that first determines the hierarchy of various correspondents: the paper size used to write the letter. Chancery papers were usually designated by their size (*qaṭ'*). The designation of the latter as a fraction of *tūmār* (2/3, 1/2, 1/3, 1/4, 1/6) dates back to the days when papyrus (*qirṭās*) was still in use.⁶² At that time, the *tūmār* (sheet of papyrus) corresponded to a sixth of a roll, and it was a common practice to designate the segment of papyrus – whose length was less than a full roll (20 sheets) – by fractions of *tūmār*.⁶³ Later on, the *tūmār* corresponded to a full sheet of paper (that is, before any cutting),⁶⁴ known in Mamluk times as *al-farḥa*.⁶⁵ The importance of these formats lies in their application insofar as they were chosen according to the status of the recipient. In addition, they determined the use of any *qalam* and the line spacing on the document.⁶⁶

Importantly, the paper size did not apply to a single sheet, but to the roll (*darj*) that would constitute the future missives,⁶⁷ which, once again

⁶² I base my discussion on the citation of al-Qalqaṣandī according to al-Madā'inī. See al-Qalqaṣandī, *Ṣubḥ al-a'sā*, VI, p. 189: «[...] *Imma 'l-ḥulafā' lam tazal tasta'milu 'l-qarā'īsa imtiyāzan lahā 'alā gayriha min 'ahdi Mu'āwiyah ibn Abī Sufyān. Wa ḍakara annahu yuktabu li 'l-ḥulafā' fī qirṭāsīn min tultay tūmār, wa ilā al-umarā' min niṣfi tūmār, wa ilā 'l-'ummāl wa 'l-kuttāb min tult, wa ilā 'l-tujjār wa ašbāhihim min rub', wa ilā 'l-ḥussāb wa 'l-mussāḥ min suds*». Geneviève Humbert, in her article “Le manuscrit arabe et ses papiers”, *RMM*, IC-C (2002): p. 71 rightly says about the commentary of al-Qalqaṣandī: «Il est clair qu'il [al-Madā'inī] veut parler du format baghdādī, qui se prête à ce type d'échelle de dimensions contrairement au shāmī, parce que Bagdad était alors le siège du califat: il ne convenait pas de mesurer à partir d'un autre papier, étant donné qu'il avait toute les qualités». She adds: «Ainsi le baghdādī, qui a signifié d'abord 'de Bagdad' avant de devenir le nom du format-étalon pour le papier, ne s'appelait probablement pas ainsi chez al-Madā'inī, et n'aurait pris ce nom qu'en s'exportant». I believe, rather, that al-Qalqaṣandī ends up amalgamating and does not take into account the fact that al-Madā'inī speaks of papyrus and not paper; as evident in his mention of *qarā'īs* and *Mu'āwiya*.

⁶³ Khan, G., “Arabic papyri”, in Dutton, Yasin (ed.), *The Codicology of Islamic Manuscripts: Proceedings of the Second Conference of Al-Furqān Islamic Heritage Foundation, 4-5 December 1993* (London: Al-Furqān Islamic Heritage Foundation 1995): p. 15. According to Grohmann, A., *From the World of Arabic Papyri* (Cairo: Al-Maaref Press, 1952): pp. 43-4.

⁶⁴ Humbert, “Le manuscrit arabe et ses papiers”: p. 70.

⁶⁵ Al-Qalqaṣandī, *Ṣubḥ al-a'sā*: VI, p. 189.

⁶⁶ To avoid digression, I will discard these considerations in the framework of this article.

⁶⁷ Humbert, “Le manuscrit arabe et ses papiers”: p. 70.

paralleled papyrus practice in previous periods.⁶⁸ In the same way, the *darj* comprised a collage of paper leaves (*waṣl*; pl. *awṣāl*) in the direction of their width or length. Such production gave rise to a roll of variable length that ran vertically. Roll width determined the format, but length depended on the number of *awṣāl*, thus being unfixed. Called *kollēsis*, the joint part of the roll was determined by paper size (0.5-2 cm), while roll width was expressed in Egyptian cubits of cloth (*bi ḍirā'ī 'l-qumāš al-miṣrī*), equivalent to 58.15 cm,⁶⁹ but was measured by finger, span or carat at times as well.⁷⁰

Paper sizes are fairly well-known thanks to al-Qalqaṣandī and al-Saḥmāwī, who describe two different practices in Egypt and Syria. Here, I will concentrate on the Egyptian rule, as this is the one to which the Mamluk chancery adhered.

n°	Al-Qalqaṣandī	Al-Saḥmāwī
1	–	<i>Qaṭ' al-tūmār al-kāmil</i> ⁷¹ (width 1,5 cubits)
2	<i>Qaṭ' al-baḡdādī al-kāmil</i> ⁷² (width: 1 cubit, length of the <i>waṣl</i> 1,5 cubits)	<i>Qaṭ' al-baḡdādī</i> ⁷³ (width: 1 cubits or sometimes 1 cubit minus 2 fingers) ⁷⁴
3	<i>Qaṭ' al-baḡdādī al-nāqīš</i> ⁷⁵ (width: 1 cubit minus 4 fingers)	
4	<i>Qaṭ' al-tuṭṭayni</i> of Egyptian paper ⁷⁶ (width: 2/3 of a cubit)	
5	<i>Qaṭ' al-niṣf</i> of Egyptian paper ⁷⁷ (width: 1/2 of a cubit)	
6	<i>Qaṭ' al-tuṭṭ</i> of Egyptian paper ⁷⁸ (width: 1/3 of a cubit)	

⁶⁸ Khan, “Arabic Papyri”: pp. 13-5.

⁶⁹ Hinz, W., *Islamische Masse und Gewichte* (Leiden: Brill, 1955): p. 56; Id., “*Ḍhirā'*”, in *EF*: II, pp. 238-9. This measurement modifies the one established by Karabacek, which was 48.8 cm. Humbert, “Le Manuscrit arabe et ses papiers”, based her measurements on this mistake.

⁷⁰ Humbert, “Le manuscrit arabe et ses papiers”: p. 72.

⁷¹ Al-Saḥmāwī, *Al-Taḡr al-bāsim*: II, p. 549.

⁷² Al-Qalqaṣandī, *Ṣubḥ al-a'ṣā*: VI, p. 190.

⁷³ Al-Saḥmāwī, *Al-Taḡr al-bāsim*: II, p. 549.

⁷⁴ According to Heidemann, S., Müller, C. & Y. Raḡib, “Un décret d'al-Malik al-'Ādil en 571/1176 relatif aux moines du Mont Sinai”, *Annales Islamologiques*, XXXI (1997): p. 85: 2 fingers = 4.504 cm. However, this paper size is very rare. It is attested only once for a letter sent to the Ḥwārizm ruler Muḥammad Ḥān in 832/1428-9: al-Saḥmāwī, *Al-Taḡr al-bāsim*: II, p. 549.

⁷⁵ Al-Qalqaṣandī, *Ṣubḥ al-a'ṣā*: VI, p. 190; Al-Saḥmāwī, *Al-Taḡr al-bāsim*: II, p. 550.

⁷⁶ Al-Qalqaṣandī, *Ṣubḥ al-a'ṣā*: VI, p. 190; Al-Saḥmāwī, *Al-Taḡr al-bāsim*: II, p. 550.

⁷⁷ Al-Qalqaṣandī, *Ṣubḥ al-a'ṣā*: VI, p. 191; Al-Saḥmāwī, *Al-Taḡr al-bāsim*: II, p. 550.

⁷⁸ Al-Qalqaṣandī, *Ṣubḥ al-a'ṣā*: VI, p. 191; Al-Saḥmāwī, *Al-Taḡr al-bāsim*: II, p. 550.

7	<i>Qaṭ' al-mansūrī</i> ⁷⁹ (width: 1/4 of a cubit)	<i>Qaṭ' al-'āda</i> ⁸⁰ (width: 1/4 of a cubit plus 1 carat)
8	<i>Qaṭ' al-ṣaḡīr</i> ou <i>Qaṭ' al-'āda</i> ⁸¹ (width: 1/6 of a cubit)	-
9	<i>Qaṭ' al-Ṣāmī al-Kāmil</i> ⁸² (width: width of a syrian <i>tūmār</i> in its length) ⁸³	-
10	<i>Qaṭ' al-Saḡīr/Waraq al-Ṭayr</i> ⁸⁴ or <i>al-Baṭā'iq</i> ⁸⁵ (width: 3 closed fingers)	
11	-	<i>Waraq al-Muṭlaqāt</i> ⁸⁶ (variable size according to the needs)

Table 3. Paper Sizes in the Egyptian System

As presented in the table above, both authors mention nine different sizes of paper used in the chancery of Cairo, depending on the type of documents and the addressee's rank. For official correspondence, however, only four sizes were in use, each categorizing Eastern foreign rulers according to Mamluks assessment:⁸⁷ *qaṭ' al-baḡdādī al-kāmil*, *qaṭ' al-niṣf*, *qaṭ' al-tuḷṭ* and *qaṭ' al-'āda*.⁸⁸

<i>Qaṭ' al-baḡdādī al-kāmil</i>	Letters to the rulers belonging to the first category ⁸⁹
<i>Qaṭ' al-niṣf</i>	Letters to the rulers belonging to the second category
<i>Qaṭ' al-tuḷṭ</i>	Letters to the rulers belonging to the third category
<i>Qaṭ' al-'āda</i>	Letters to the rulers belonging to the fourth category

Table 4. Categories of Foreign Rulers During the Turkish Period

⁷⁹ Al-Qalqaṣandī, *Ṣubḥ al-a'ṣā*: VI, p. 191.

⁸⁰ Al-Saḥmāwī, *Al-Ṭaḡr al-bāsim*: II, p. 550.

⁸¹ Al-Qalqaṣandī, *Ṣubḥ al-a'ṣā*: VI p. 191.

⁸² Ibid.: VI, p. 191.

⁸³ Al-Qalqaṣandī, *Ṣubḥ al-a'ṣā*: VI, p. 191. I have found no information on this measure.

⁸⁴ Ibid.: VI, p. 191.

⁸⁵ Al-Saḥmāwī, *Al-Ṭaḡr al-bāsim*: II, p. 551.

⁸⁶ Ibid.: II, p. 551.

⁸⁷ Al-Qalqaṣandī, *Ṣubḥ al-a'ṣā*: VIII, p. 20; Ibid.: VI, pp. 190-2; al-Saḥmāwī, *Al-Ṭaḡr al-bāsim*: II, p. 550.

⁸⁸ As mentioned in the table, al-Qalqaṣandī and al-Saḥmāwī assign two different measures for the *qaṭ' al-'ādah*: 1/6 of cubit and 1/4 of cubit. I believe that al-Qalqaṣandī's *qaṭ' al-'ādah* is indeed his *qaṭ' al-mansūrī* which is 1/4 of cubit. Only the *qaṭ' al-ṣaḡīr* is 1/6 of cubit. See my Ph.D. dissertation, *Le Caire carrefour des ambassades*: p. 310.

⁸⁹ These categories will receive further attention below.

This hierarchization into four categories of rulers was attested during the Turkish period, but during the Circassian, only the last three remained.⁹⁰

<i>Qaṭ' al-niṣf</i>	Letters to the rulers belonging to the first category
<i>Qaṭ' al-tuḷṭ</i>	Letters to the rulers belonging to the second category
<i>Qaṭ' al-'āda</i>	Letters to the rulers belonging to the third category

Table 5. Categories of Foreign Rulers During the Circassian Period

2. Blank spaces rule: *ṭurra*

Among other material elements that determine addressees' status is the *ṭurra*, which corresponds to all sheets (*awṣāl*) left blank at the beginning of the roll, before the first line of the text (*basmala*). For a long time, it was also considered dependent on the paper size because of a rule al-Qalqaṣandī describes:⁹¹

<i>Qaṭ' al-baġdādī al-kāmil</i>	6 blank <i>awṣāl</i> – the <i>basmala</i> at the beginning of the 7th
<i>Qaṭ' al-tuḷṭayn</i>	5 blank <i>awṣāl</i> – the <i>basmala</i> at the beginning of the 6th
<i>Qaṭ' al-niṣf</i>	4 blank <i>awṣāl</i> – the <i>basmala</i> at the beginning of the 5th
<i>Qaṭ' al-tuḷṭ</i>	3 blank <i>awṣāl</i> – the <i>basmala</i> at the beginning of the 4th
<i>Qaṭ' al-'āda</i>	3 or 2 blank <i>awṣāl</i> – the <i>basmala</i> at the beginning of the following <i>waṣl</i>

Table 6. Rules for Use of Blank Space

However, sample documents preserved in the chancery manuals reveal that this rule was rarely followed, the *ṭurra* generally being shorter than it should have been. Indeed, another rule seems to prevail, and it corresponds to the sultan's *tarjama* (his signature): namely the '*alāma*. Three different formulas were used by the sultan to sign a document: *aḥūhu* (his brother), *wāliduhu* (his father), or his personal name.⁹² According to al-Qalqaṣandī, the *ṭurra* is generally 3 blank sheets *awṣāl* on documents signed by the first two formulas but only 2 blank sheets *waṣl* on documents signed by the sultan's name.⁹³ Analysis of letter samples in the manual shows that this rule was the one used by the secretaries in the Cairo chancery.

⁹⁰ Only a few exceptions for the use of the paper *baġdādī al-kāmil* are attested during the Circassian period. Al-Saḥmāwī, *Al-Taġr al-bāsim*: II, p. 772.

⁹¹ Al-Qalqaṣandī, *Ṣubḥ al-a'ṣā*: VI, pp. 195, 314

⁹² I will come back to these formulas in the section devoted to the signature.

⁹³ Al-Qalqaṣandī, *Ṣubḥ al-a'ṣā*: VIII, p. 21; *Ibid.*: VI, p. 314.

3. Opening formulas (iftitāh)

Apart from the document's external characteristics that determine the primary categories of Eastern foreign rulers, internal features allow further distinction of sub-categories. These internal features comprise formulary elements within the letters themselves, which usually appear concentrated in the introductory protocol. The first consists of the opening formulas.

After the time-honored expression of the *basmala*, the Mamluk chancery employed two different means for opening letters, both dependent on addressee's status. The first, called *huṭba*, corresponds to the use of *fawātiḥ*⁹⁴ (*ḥamdala-tašahhud-taṣliya-ba'diyya* or *ba'diyya-ḥamdala-tašahhud-taṣliya*), and appeared most often in the Turkish period for writing to the most important Eastern rulers, like those of the Khanates. The last example of this formula's usage comes from the letters sent to Tīmūr.⁹⁵ During the Circassian period however, this way to open letters gave way to the use of invocations (*du'ā'*, pl. *ad'iya*) for greeting correspondent and expressing the sender's good wishes and intentions.

Such an opening generally involves invoking God in the addressee's name. In the introductory protocol, invocations both precede and follow the address of the document (*intitulatio*: *'unwān*), at times found even in the letter's final protocol. The *du'ā'* is characterized by the use of a verb that either expresses a wish or hope in the optative form, or evokes the concept of continuity or perpetuity, such as the verbs *lā zāla*, *lā bariḥa*.⁹⁶ A formula normally related to the meaning of the message, the *du'ā'* undergoes specific formulation according to recipient status. The use of a particular word is very significant, and very early on the scribes understood the importance of these formulas and further developed the invocation in their textbooks.

During the Ayyubid period, the formula *lā zāla-lā bariḥa* was the sultan's prerogative when he addressed his counterparts, but during the Mamluk period, it became more widely used, though always in the letters addressed to important rulers (or governor and notables).⁹⁷ Scribes preferred other kinds of invocations, however, that established the addressee's status more precisely: the invocations *fī 'l-'uluww wa 'l-hubūṭ*. Such formulas betray several assessments—the existence, benefits, victory and power of the addressee—and consist of a wish for longevity, glory, tenfold increase, or perpetuity.⁹⁸ Moreover, each assessment contains a hierarchy of terms

⁹⁴ Ibid.: VI, pp. 224-31; al-Saḥmāwī, *Al-Taḡr al-bāsim*: II, pp. 557-8.

⁹⁵ Al-Qalqašandī, *Ṣubḥ al-a'šā*: VII, pp. 308, 320, 325; al-Saḥmāwī, *Al-Taḡr al-bāsim*: II, p. 744.

⁹⁶ Gully, A., *The Culture of Letter-Writing* (Edinburgh: University Press, 2008): p. 167.

⁹⁷ Al-Qalqašandī, *Ṣubḥ al-a'šā*: VI, p. 287.

⁹⁸ Ibid.: VI, pp. 284-5; Al-Saḥmāwī, *Al-Taḡr al-bāsim*: II, pp. 635-6.

used to express it (e.g., *iṭālat al-baqā'* > *iṭālat al-'umr*; *'izz al-anṣār* > *'izz al-naṣr* > *'izz al-nuṣra*; *muḏā'afat al-ni'ma* > *dawām al-ni'ma*, etc.).

Letters to the rulers belonging to the first category ⁹⁹	<i>Ḥutba-Fawātiḥ</i> ; <i>Zīdat 'aḏamatuhu</i> or <i>dāmat ma'dilatuhu</i>
Letters to the rulers belonging to the second category	<i>'izz al-anṣār</i> > <i>iṭālat al-baqā'</i> > <i>dawām al-sulṭān</i> , <i>ḥulūd al-mulk</i> We can also encounter the <i>lā zāla</i> , <i>lā bariḥa</i> formula
Letters to the rulers belonging to the third category	<i>'izz al-naṣr</i> ¹⁰⁰ > <i>'izz al-nuṣra</i> > <i>mudāwamat al-nuṣra</i>
Letters to the rulers belonging to the fourth category	<i>muḏā'afat al-ni'ma</i> > <i>mudāwamat al-ni'ma</i>

Table 7. Invocation Formula in the Turkish Period

During the Circassian period only the last three categories are attested:

Letters to the rulers belonging to the first category	<i>'izz al-anṣār</i> > <i>iṭālat al-baqā'</i> > <i>dawām al-sulṭān</i> , <i>ḥulūd al-mulk</i> . We can also encounter the <i>lā zāla</i> , <i>lā bariḥa</i> formula
Letters to the rulers belonging to the second category	<i>'izz al-naṣr</i> > <i>'izz al-nuṣra</i> > <i>mudāwamat al-nuṣra</i>
Letters to the rulers belonging to the third category	<i>muḏā'afat al-ni'ma</i> > <i>mudāwamat al-ni'ma</i>

Table 8. Invocation Formula in the Circassian Period

4. The honorary titles (*alqāb* and *nu'ūt*)

Directly following the invocations come the addressee's titles, which – more than anything else – define the recipient's status with great precision. The attribution of titles held a very important place in the secretaries' eyes. For this reason, al-Qalqašandī and al-Saḥmāwī devoted entire sections (*bāb*) of their works to the explanation and classification of these titles.¹⁰¹

Laqab (pl. *alqāb*) was originally a nickname used to designate a negative characteristic of the person addressed, as opposed to *na't* (pl. *nu'ūt*), which would characterize the person's best qualities. Over time, the two tended to describe positive qualities rather than defects. The scribes therefore distinguished between them, with *laqab* becoming an adjective expressed

⁹⁹ I will come back to those categories later on.

¹⁰⁰ Al-Qalqašandī, *Ṣubḥ al-a'šā'*: VI, p. 285; Al-Saḥmāwī, *Al-Taḡr al-bāsim*: II, pp. 636-7. During the Ayyubid period, the invocations *'izz al-naṣr* and *muḏā'afat al-iqtidār* were proper to the sultan.

¹⁰¹ Sublet, J., *Le voile du nom. Essai sur le nom propre arabe* (Paris: PUF, 1991): pp. 7-38; 39-56; 157-94.

with a single word (e.g., *al-malik*) and *na't* becoming a compound adjective comprised of several conjoined words (e.g., *sayf amīr al-mu'minīn*).¹⁰² This practice of designating people by their qualities, profession or rank rather than their names goes back to the early history of the Arabs, and it underwent important developments from the time of the Prophet Muḥammad to the Mamluk era. In the case of Egypt, not until the Fatimid period did rulers introduce this practice into their hierarchy, after which time it gradually developed with the increase of government functions and ultimately culminated during the Mamluk period. Rules of usage for these adjectives are fairly well-attested in chancery manuals, especially those of al-Qalqaṣandī and al-Saḥmāwī. Researchers in diplomatic and political history must understand these rules properly, for along with the study of paper, they enable absolute definition to define of the correspondent's status as well as perception of other and self alike. We find seven chief titles used in the Mamluk chancery, all referring to places, *alqāb makāniyya*:

al-ḥaḍra > *al-jānib* > *al-maqām* >
al-maqarr > *al-janāb* > *al-majlis* > *majlis*.¹⁰³

During the Circassian period, four principal titles were in use: *al-maqām* > *al-maqarr* > *al-janāb* > *al-majlis*. Secondary titles then followed (*al-alqāb al-mufarra'a*) that allowed for further specification of the addressee's rank since several levels of importance existed within each category of ruler. Five secondary titles mark these differences:

al-ašraf > *al-šarīf* > *al-karīm* > *al-'ālī* > *al-sāmī*¹⁰⁴

I	<i>Al-Maqām</i>	1	<i>Al-Maqām al-ašraf (al-'ālī)</i>
		2	<i>Al-Maqām al-šarīf (al-'ālī)</i>
		3	<i>Al-Maqām al-'ālī</i>
I'	<i>Al-Maqarr</i>	1	<i>Al-Maqarr al-karīm (al-'ālī)</i>
		2	<i>Al-Maqarr al-'ālī</i>
II	<i>Al-Janāb</i>	1	<i>Al-Janāb al-karīm (al-'ālī)</i>
		2	<i>Al-Janāb al-'ālī</i>
		1	<i>Al-Majlis al-'ālī</i>

¹⁰² Al-Qalqaṣandī, *Ṣubḥ al-a'šā*: V, p. 439.

¹⁰³ Ibid.: V, pp. 493-502; Al-Saḥmāwī, *Al-Taḡr al-bāsim*: I, pp. 515-22.

¹⁰⁴ Al-Qalqaṣandī, *Ṣubḥ al-a'šā*: VI, pp. 115-6; Al-Saḥmāwī, *Al-Taḡr al-bāsim*: I, pp. 515-22.

III	<i>Al-Majlis</i>	2	<i>Al-Majlis al-sāmī</i>	with <i>yā'</i>
				without <i>yā'</i>

Table 9. Secondary Titles

Only the association of “principal *laqab* – secondary *laqab*” determines the addressee’s rank. The following titles specify other functions he might have. The secondary title ordinarily preceded the *laqab al-wazīfa*, which states the addressee’s position (i.e., military or civil: *al-amīr*, *al-šayḥ*).¹⁰⁵ Then comes the *laqab al-kabīr(ī)* followed by a title establishing the addressee’s function (e.g., *al-kāfīl(ī)*, *al-wazīr(ī)*, *al-ḥākīm(ī)*,...). After this *laqab*, a list of titles appear whose length can vary, whose order and arrangement depends on the secretary’s pen,¹⁰⁶ and whose end is marked by a title of recognition that names the addressee (*al-fulānī* or *fulān al-dīn*). This last title is the point of junction between the *alqāb* and *nu ‘ūt*.

Principal *laqab*-secondary *laqab*-[*al-mawlawī*]-*laqab al-wazīfa*-
al-kabīr(ī)- *laqab* of function-[...]-*laqab(ī)*-*laqab(ī)*-
 [...]-*laqab(ī)*-[...] -*al-fulānī* [*al-dīn*]-*nu ‘ūt*.¹⁰⁷

The *nu ‘ūt* are compound titles formed on *iḍāfa* with two terms or more,¹⁰⁸ which also depend on the addressee’s rank. After the *laqab* of recognition comes a *na ‘t* associated with the religion of Islam (e.g., *rukn al-islām wa ‘l-muslimīn*; *‘izz al-islām wa ‘l-muslimīn*). Here, too, a hierarchy emerges between the formulas (e.g., *mu ‘izz al-islām wa ‘l-muslimīn* > *rukn al-islām wa ‘l-muslimīn*).¹⁰⁹ The *nu ‘ūt*’s list should end with a title related to the ruler (caliph or/and sultan), such as *ḡahīr al-mulūk wa ‘l-salāṭīn*, *qasīm amīr al-mu ‘minīn*.¹¹⁰ Between the first and the last *na ‘t* lie many other titles corresponding to the addressee’s position or function, whose exact organization depends on the secretary’s pen.

Principal *laqab*-secondary *laqab*-[*al-mawlawī*]-
laqab al-wazīfa- *al-kabīr(ī)*-

¹⁰⁵ However, it is preceded by the title “*al-mawlawī*” at times: Al-Qalqašandī, *Šubḥ al-a ‘šā*: VI, p. 116.

¹⁰⁶ Ibid.: VI, p. 118.

¹⁰⁷ Concerning the (ī), it corresponds to the *yā'* of the *nisba*. Its use amplifies the value of the status because it reinforces the qualificative meaning (*šīḡat mubālaḡa*): Al-Qalqašandī, *Šubḥ al-a ‘šā*: V, pp. 503-4.

¹⁰⁸ Ibid.: V, p. 505.

¹⁰⁹ Ibid.: VI, pp. 102-3.

¹¹⁰ Ibid.: VI, pp. 106-8.

laqab of function-[...]-*laqab(ī)*-*laqab(ī)*-[...]-*laqab(ī)*-
[...]-*al-fulānī* [*al-dīn*]-*na 't al-islām*-[...]-[...]-[...]-*na 't al-mulūk*/
al-salātīn/amīr al-mu'minīn

5. The salutatio

One final element belonging to the introductory protocol typically reveals addressee status: the *salutatio*, a formula that closes the opening protocol and greets the addressee. In Mamluk letters, the *salutatio* is generally introduced by a formula expressing the publication of the letter and reiterating the addressee's titles. This formula precedes two other: the *taslīm* and the introductory part of the message itself.

The publication formula is characterized by the use of the verb *šadara* (to emanate/to be issued), which could be conjugated in different ways as required.¹¹¹ Four main formulas emerge from the chancery manuals:¹¹²

*ašdarnāhā ilā > ašdarnā hādīhi 'l-mukātaba ilā > ušdirat ilā >
šadarat ilā*

However, other formulas are attested in sample letters as well, formulas such as *ašdarnā hādīhi 'l-muḡāwaḡa ilā*, *ušdirat hādīhi 'l-mukātaba ilā*, *šadarat hādīhi 'l-mukātaba ilā*, *šadarat hādīhi 'l-muḡāwaḡa ilā* or simply *hādīhi 'l-mukātaba ilā*, *hādīhi 'l-muḡāwaḡa ilā*. Over time, the deployment of *muḡāwaḡa* became more widespread than *mukātaba* in letters addressed to important rulers. After the preposition *ilā* come the addressee's titles, similar to those used previously, but in their simple form: principal *laqab* – secondary *laqab*. Then comes the *taslīm* formula: *nuḡdī/tuḡdī ilayhi salāman* [...], followed by one or two sentences intended to show the author's good intentions towards the addressee. This formula constitutes the *salutatio* strictly speaking.

Finally, a final formula closes the introduction to the text of the letter, that text being the message itself. The formula could employ one of two verbs: “to reveal” (*abdā*) or “to clarify” (*waḡḡaḡa*), combined to the word ‘*ilm* and an adjective that reminds the reader of the addressee's status (*al-šarīf*, *al-karīm*,...).¹¹³ The verb *abdā* conveys a higher in status than *waḡḡaḡa*:

nu-/tuḡdī li 'ilmīhi 'l-šarīf > nu-/tuwaḡḡiḡu li 'ilmīhi 'l-karīm

¹¹¹ Ibid.: VI, p. 341. This practice goes back to the Seljukid period and was followed by the Ayyubids as well.

¹¹² Ibid.: VI, p. 280; al-Saḡmāwī, *Al-Taḡr al-bāsim*: II, p. 634.

¹¹³ Al-Qalqašandī, *Šubḡ al-a'šā*: VI, p. 281; al-Saḡmāwī, *Al-Taḡr al-bāsim*: II, p. 634.

6. The signature

The appended signature belongs to neither the external nor the internal characteristics of the letter but bears a relationship to both. Be that as it may, it also indicates the addressee's status as seen by the Mamluks. There were two different ways to sign documents and letters in the Mamluk chancery of Cairo: the *tuḡrāh* and the *'alāma*. Yet again, status of addressee determines formulation used. A practice inherited from the Turkish tradition via the Seljukids and then the Ayyubids,¹¹⁴ the *tuḡrāh* required good calligraphic skills, and thus a specific person (*rajul mufrad*) was assigned its production. This person prepared them in advance on a separate sheet of paper that was attached to the top of the letters before they were sent. The *tuḡrāh* was used in the letters addressed to Infidel rulers, including the Ilkhanids.¹¹⁵ The last testimony of the use of the *tuḡrāh* is attested in the letters addressed to Tīmūr.¹¹⁶

The most widespread signature used in the Mamluk chancery is the *'alāma*. The *'alāma*-signature demands distinction from the *'alāma-motto* in use during the Fatimid and Ayyubid periods.¹¹⁷ Even though Mamluk secretaries still knew the latter, they rarely deployed it, except in the *manšūr* (allocation of landed property), and sometimes in letters addressed to the Khanate rulers: *Allāh amaī*.¹¹⁸ By contrast, the *'alāma*-signature occurs to be widely on documents and letters during this period. We can recognize three different signatures appended by the sultan himself on the top of the letters,¹¹⁹ between the second and the third lines of the text:

*aḡūhu > wāliduhu > ism.*¹²⁰

Since the *tuḡrāh* belonged to rulers of the first category (among whom the Ilkhanids) during the Turkish period and this signature no longer arises during the Circassian period, the *'alāma* classification then falls into three categories:

<i>Aḡūhu</i>	Appended for the 1st category of rulers.
<i>Wāliduhu</i>	Appended for the 2nd category of rulers.
<i>Ism</i>	Appended for the 3rd category of rulers.

¹¹⁴ Stern, S.M., *Fāṭimid Decrees. Original Documents from the Fāṭimid Chancery* (London: Faber & Faber, 1964): pp. 144, 148.

¹¹⁵ Even after their conversion to Islam.

¹¹⁶ Al-Qalqašandī, *Ṣubḥ al-a'šā*: VII, pp. 319-20 et 325.

¹¹⁷ Stern, *Fāṭimid Decrees*: pp. 124-30.

¹¹⁸ Al-Saḡmāwī, *al-Taḡr al-bāsim*: II, pp. 646-7.

¹¹⁹ Ibid.: II, p. 646.

¹²⁰ Al-Qalqašandī, *Ṣubḥ al-a'šā*: VI, p. 314; Heidemann, Müller & Raḡib, "Un décret d'al-Malik al-'Ādil": p. 86.

7. *Categories of rulers*

Returning to the four categories of rulers expressed above,¹²¹ al-Qalqašandī clearly refers to them when defining the paper appropriate for various official correspondences.¹²² Having analyzed the letter samples presented in the five main chancery manuals and classified them according to those rules outlined above, I observed that such categorization corresponds not only to paper but also to opening formulas, invocations, titles, *salutatio* and signature. The basis of this division goes back to the Turkish period, established by al-‘Umarī and later Ibn Nāzīr al-Jayš. During the Circassian period, it continues but in a form related to the new geopolitical environment.

For the first period, four main categories classify Muslim sovereigns in the East: (1) those from the Khanates (later on, after the Ilkhanids’ fall, their successors, the Jalayrids); (2) the main Ilkhanid governor (the emir-*ulus*); (3) the other Ilkhanid governors (from military class, like the Jalayirids or the Chobanids) and some Ilkhanid clients (Germiyān in Anatolia); and (4) minor Ilkhanid client-dynasties in the Upper Euphrates and Anatolia.

As for the Circassian period, new data cannot always be easily distinguished from old, as the former are often incorporated into the latter, namely, data taken up from the manuals of al-‘Umarī and Ibn Nāzīr al-Jayš. Al-Qalqašandī, for instance, presents hardly any new information apart from that concerning Tīmūr. The most important source for this period comes from al-Saḥmāwī. In his work, the first category described for the Turkish period no longer exists, and only three categories remain: (1) the Ilkhanids’ successors in Iran, Azerbaijan and Iraq (the Jalayirids and later the Timurids, Qara Qoyunlu and – after the capture of Constantinople – the Ottomans); (2) the Beyliks of Anatolia (like the Qaramanids) and, at the beginning of their ascent, the Ottomans (Murād I); and (3) minor Turkmen and Kurdish dynasties from Anatolia, Upper Euphrates, Iraq al-‘Ajam who are clients of the second group mentioned in the mid-fifteenth century (the Aq Qoyunlu confederation).

When looking at diplomatic rules associated with the definition of the status (paper, titles, invocations, *salutatio*, *‘alāma*) during the Circassian period, we see that several levels exist within each category of ruler.

¹²¹ All the rules examined concern Eastern Muslim rulers.

¹²² See above, point (1).

N°	paper	Title		Invocation	Salutatio	'Alāma	
I	<i>al-niṣf</i>	1	<i>al-maqām al-ṣarīf</i>	<i>a'azza 'llāh anṣār</i>	<i>aṣdarnā(hā)</i>	<i>aḥūhu</i>	
		2	<i>al-maqām al-'ālī</i>				
		3	<i>al-maqarr al-karīm</i>	<i>a'azza 'llāh anṣār</i>	-		<i>muḥāwaḍa</i>
				<i>a'azza 'llāh nuṣrat</i>	-		<i>abdā</i>
		4	<i>al-maqarr al-'ālī</i>	<i>a'azza 'llāh anṣār</i>			
				<i>a'azza 'llāh nuṣrat</i>			
II	<i>al-tuḷṭ</i>	1	<i>al-janāb al- karīm</i>	<i>a'azza 'llāh anṣār</i>	<i>ṣadarat hāḍihi 'l- mukātaba</i>	<i>aḥūhu</i>	
				<i>adāma 'llāh naṣr/nuṣrat</i>			
				<i>ḍā'afa 'llāh ni'mat</i>		-	-
		2	<i>al-janāb al- 'ālī</i>	<i>ḍā'afa 'llāh ni'mat</i>	<i>waḍḍaḥa</i>	<i>wāliduhu</i>	
				<i>adāma 'llāh ni'mat</i>			
III	<i>al-'āda</i>	1	<i>al-majlis al- 'ālī</i>	<i>adāma 'llāh ni'mat</i>	<i>ṣadarat</i>	<i>aḥūhu</i>	
		2	<i>al-majlis al- sāmī</i>	<i>adāma 'llāh ni'mat</i>		- <i>wāliduhu</i>	

Table 10. Categories of Rulers During the Circassian Period

c) Practice

Having presented a theoretical framework of the diplomatic rules, I will now focus on their application in the ms. ar. 4440 corpus and attempt to confirm or modify the portrait of Mamluk-Timurid relations as reflected in the chronicles and letters.¹²³

1. Letter V (Jaqmaq > Šāh Ruḥ)

Paper size	Not mentioned
Addressee's titles	<i>Al-Maqām 'l-šarīf 'l-Mu 'inī Šāh Ruḥ b. Timur-Lank</i>
Opening invocation	<i>Lā zāla, lā bariḥa</i>
salutatio	<i>ašdarna hādīhi 'l-mufūwaḍa 'ilā 'l-maqāmi 'l-šarīf tuhdī ilayhi salāman [...]</i>
	<i>wa tubdī li šarīf 'ilmika anna ...</i>
'Alāma	Not mentioned

2. Letter XXIV (Jaqmaq > Muḥammad Jūkī)

Paper size	<i>Qaṭ' al-niṣf</i>
Addressee's titles	<i>Al-Maqarr 'l-karīm 'l-'ālī 'l-amīrī 'l-kabīrī (until the end)</i> ¹²⁴
Opening invocation	<i>A'azza 'llāh ta'ālā anšāra 'l-Maqarri 'l-karīmi</i>
salutatio	<i>nubdīhi li 'ilmīhi 'l-karīm anna...</i>
'Alāma	<i>Aḥūhu</i>

3. Letter XLIII (Jaqmaq > 'Alā' al-Dawla)

Paper size	Not mentioned
Addressee's titles	<i>Al-šayḥ 'l-imām 'l-'ālim 'l-fādīl 'l-wara' 'l-zāhid 'l-'ābid 'l-nāsik 'l-ḥāsi' 'l-bāri' 'l-quṭb 'l-ḥāfiḥ šayḥ al-mašā'ih ḡaḍī 'l-šulahā' malja' al-awliyā' murabbī 'l-atqiyā' ḡiyāt al-islām wa 'l-muslimīn šams al-'arīfīn quṭb al-'ālamīn jamāl al-muttaqīn qudwat al-zāhidīn majdat al-šāliḥīn muršid al-sā'ihīn farīd 'aṣrihi wa zamānīni wa waḥīd dahrihi wa awānīni sal 'anhu wa</i>

¹²³ In the present analysis, I do not take into account letter XLI from Šāh Ruḥ to Jaqmaq, since it is a production of the Timurid chancery and therefore differs from the rules of the Mamluk chancery as described above. All the other letters are presented in their chronological order.

¹²⁴ This is a note added by the scribe who neglected to give the rest of the *alqāb*.

	<i>'nṭuq bihi wa 'nzur ilayhi tajid mala 'a 'l-masāmi' wa 'l-afwāhwa 'l-muqill</i>
Opening invocation (1)	<i>lā zāla-lā bariḥa</i>
<i>salutatio</i> (1)	<i>ṣadara yuhdī ilayhi salāman</i>
	<i>wa yuwaḍḍiḥu li 'ilmihī 'l-karīm anna [...]</i>
Opening invocation (2)	<i>Adāma 'llāh ta'ālā 'l-naḥ'a bi barakati 'l-šayḥi 'l-imāmi [...]</i>
<i>salutatio</i> (2)	<i>ṣadarat hādīhi 'l-mukātaba ilayhi muntawīya 'alā salām [...]</i>
	<i>yuwaḍḍiḥu li 'ilmihī 'l-mubārak [...]</i>
<i>'Alāma</i>	<i>Wāliduhu</i>

4. Letter XLII (Jağmaq > Šāh Ruḥ)

Paper size	Not mentioned
Addressee's titles	<i>Al-Maqām 'l-šarīf 'l-'ālī 'l-'ālamī 'l-mujāhidī 'l-malāḍī 'l-mu'īnī nuṣrat al-dīn malja' al-qāšidīna kanz al-fuqahā' wa 'l-masākīn ḍuḥr amīri 'l-mu'minīn</i>
Opening invocation	<i>A'azza 'llāh ta'ālā anšāra 'l-Maqāmi 'l-šarīfi 'l-'ālī</i>
	<i>Lā zāla-lā bariḥa</i>
<i>salutatio</i>	<i>ṣadarat hādīhi 'l-mufāwāda ilā 'l-Maqāmi 'l-šarīf [...]</i> <i>wa nuhdī ilayhi salāman [...]</i>
	<i>wa yubdī li 'ilmikum al-šarīf [...]</i>
<i>'Alāma</i>	Not mentioned

5. Letter LXII (Jağmaq > Muḥammad Jūkī)

Paper size	Not mentioned
Addressee's titles	<i>Al-maqām 'l-'ālī 'l-kabīri 'l-'ālamī 'l-'ādilī 'l-mu'ayyadī 'l-za'īmī 'l-mumahhidī 'l-ḡahīri 'l-nāširi mu'izzal-islām wa 'l-muslimīn nāšir al-ḡuzāt wa ḥibr al-mujāhidīn malja' al-fuqarā' wa 'l-masākīn za'īm juyūši 'l-muwahḥidīn 'aḍud amīri 'l-mu'minīn wa adāma 'alā a'dā'ihī 'qtidārahu</i>
Opening invocation	<i>A'azza 'llāh ta'ālā anšāra 'l-maqāmi 'l-'ālī (...)</i>
	<i>Lā zāla-lā bariḥa</i>
<i>salutatio</i>	<i>aṣdarnāhā ilā 'l-maqāmi 'l-'ālī tuhdī ilayhi salāman wa tanā'an</i>

	<i>wa tubdī li 'ilmīhi 'l-karīm anna (...)</i>
'Alāma	Not mentioned

6. Letter XLIV (Jaqmaq > 'Alā' al-Dawla)

Paper size	<i>Qaṭ' al-tuṭ</i>
Addressee's titles	<i>al-Janāb 'l-karīm</i>
Opening invocation	<i>Lā zāla-lā bariḥa</i>
salutatio	<i>ṣadarat 'ilā 'l-janābi 'l-karīm tuhdī ilayhi salāman</i>
	<i>wa tuwaḍḍiḥu li 'ilmīhi 'l-karīm anna [...]</i>
'Alāma	<i>Wāliduhu</i>

A comparative table pulls the differences between the various correspondents into sharper contrast:

Šāh Ruḥ	Muḥammad Jūkī	'Alā' al-Dawla
-	<i>Qaṭ' al-Niṣf</i>	<i>Qaṭ' al-Tuṭ</i>
<i>Al-maqām al-šarīf</i>	<i>Al-maqarr al-karīm</i>	<i>Al-šayḥ</i>
-	<i>Al-maqām al-'ālī</i>	<i>Al-janāb al-karīm</i>
<i>'Izz al-anṣār</i>	<i>'Izz al-anṣār</i>	<i>dawām al-naḥ</i>
<i>Lā zāla- lā bariḥa</i>	<i>Lā zāla - lā bariḥa</i>	<i>Lā zāla - lā bariḥa</i>
<i>'Aṣdarnā hāḍiḥi al-mufāwaḍa</i>	<i>'Aṣdarnāhā</i>	<i>Ṣadarat hāḍiḥi al-mukātaba</i>
<i>Ṣadarat hāḍiḥi al-mufāwaḍa</i>	-	<i>Ṣadarat</i>
<i>Tubdī li-šarīf 'ilmikum</i>	<i>Nubdīhi li-'ilmīhi al-karīm</i>	<i>Yuwaḍḍiḥu li-'ilmīhi al-mubārak</i>
<i>Yubdī li-'ilmikum al-šarīf</i>	<i>Tubdī li-'ilmīhi al-karīm</i>	<i>Yuwaḍḍiḥu li-'ilmīhi al-karīm</i>

Table 11. A Comparative Chart of Correspondence

Comparison of these features with the rules related to addressee status reveals that both Šāh Ruḥ and Muḥammad Jūkī belong to the first category of sovereigns described for the Circassian period. However, within this group the Mamluks consider the two of different rank. As *al-maqām al-šarīf*, Šāh Ruḥ occupies the first level, while Muḥammad Jūkī finds himself on the second. His case is particularly interesting given his

promotion between letters XXIV and LXII. Though first addressed as *al-maqarr al-karīm*, the third level of the first category, he then receives address as *al-maqām al-‘ālī*, the second level of this group. As far as ‘Alā’ al-Dawla is concerned, an anomaly arises. Whereas letter XLIII designates him as *al-šayḥ al-imām*, the letter’s actual contents seem to refer to the Samarqandī šayḥ who came to Cairo in the year 845/1442. ‘Alā’ al-Dawla was not a šayḥ himself. A couple possibilities might account for this title. Either the secretary who wrote the letter wrongly attributed this title to ‘Alā’ al-Dawla, which could reflect a certain ignorance concerning the Timurid dynasty, or the letter was not addressed to ‘Alā’ al-Dawla at all, and the scribe who copied the letter into ms. ar. 4440 simply transcribed it incorrectly. Since no evidence suggests that ‘Alā’ al-Dawla had been in Samarqand, he would presumably not have corresponded with the Mamluks on the matter, unless the šayḥ first stopped in Herat on his way back home. Given the lack of information, I am forced to leave this question open. The title used in letter XLIV is less ambiguous: *al-janāb al-karīm*. Such a designation corresponds to the first level of the second category of sovereigns.

As far as paper is concerned, the corpus mentions two sizes: *al-nisf* for Muḥammad Jūkī and *al-tult* for ‘Alā’ al-Dawla. These measurements exhibit an exact correlation with their respective categories: first and second. According to the principle outlined above, the two letters addressed to Šāh Ruḥ would have been written on an *al-nisf* paper. The rules related to the invocations, *salutatio*, and *‘alāma* also confirm the Timurids’ status. Used for all three Timurid correspondents, the invocation *lā zāla-lā bariḥa* does not help determine the ruler’s rank, unlike the invocation *fī ‘l-‘uluww wa ‘l-hubūt*, where *a‘azza ‘llāh ta‘ālā anšār* applies only to the first category of rulers (Šāh Ruḥ and Muḥammad Jūkī). No information recounts the invocation addressed to ‘Alā’ al-Dawla in letter XLIV, but it could be *a‘azza ‘llāh anšār*, *adāma ‘llāh naṣr/nuṣrat*, or *ḍā‘afa ‘llāh ni‘mat*. Considering the *‘alāma* used for him is only *wāliduhu*, however, *a‘azza ‘llāh ta‘ālā* loses its viability. The *‘alāma* for Muḥammad Jūkī is *aḥūhu*, and it might have been the same for Šāh Ruḥ. Finally, the choice of formulas in the *salutatio* conforms to the rule outlined as well: *aṣḍarnā-aṣḍarnāhā-mufāwaḍa / abdā* appears for the rulers of the first category, while *ṣadarat-mukātaba / waḍḍaḥa* occurs for the rulers of the second one.

III. CONCLUSION

In this article, I have concentrated on the state of diplomatic relations between the Mamluks and Timurids in the 15th century, primarily from a Mamluk perspective. After briefly overviewing a tumultuous period between them – first military and then epistolary – I have focused on a

corpus of chancery letters exchanged between Jaqmaq and Šāhruḥids. Based on that corpus as well as the chronicles, I stated that Mamluk–Timurid relations improved during the reign of Jaqmaq, – and significantly so when compared to that of Barqūq or Barsbāy. However, historical study alone is not sufficient to judge the true state of relations. I therefore availed myself of diplomatics and contemporary chancery manuals to establish a means of ascertaining the Mamluk perspective on the Timurids.

Through analysis of paper size, invocations, titleholders, *salutatio*, and signature, I have concluded that the Mamluks did not consider all Timurid rulers equal. Šāh Ruḥ is the most important ruler, belonging to the first level of the first category of sovereigns. While also part of this same group, his son Muḥammad Jūkī occupies its third and then second level. Notably, he is the only son of Šāh Ruḥ’s known to Mamluk authors. ‘Alā’ al-Dawla, Šāh Ruḥ’s grandson, is considered part of only the second group of rulers. Moreover, while the Mamluk chronicles seem to have no knowledge of him (I have found no mention of him within them), even in the correspondence preserved, Mamluk secretaries misunderstand his status, mistaking him for a šayḥ in letter XLIII. When compared with other Eastern Muslim rulers, the Timurids during the reign of Šāh Ruḥ have pride of place among those rulers in contact with the Mamluks. At this time, the Qara Qoyunlu may constitute part of the first category of sovereigns, yet Jahānšāh only benefits from the third level within this group.

Since Tīmūr’s entrance in Syria under Faraj and the diplomatic struggle between Šāh Ruḥ and Barsbāy, Mamluk-Timurid relations improved substantially, yielding mutual respect and recognition. With the accounts of embassy exchange recorded in the Mamluk chronicles and the contents of letters transmitted in the ms. ar. 4440, the portrait of relations has become not only more vivid but also more accurate. As I sought to show in this article, however, diplomatic analysis is essential for determining the state and nature of such relations with greater precision. The magnitude of those details provided by diplomatics only reinforces the great need of this discipline in historical study. Application of this reading grid has evinced that form is often as important as content, that the *how* merits attention equal to the *what*.

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